

Stakeholder identification (PLUS CHANGE)

Background: Stakeholders are an essential part of the Plus Change project, so it is important to identify different groups of stakeholders. This form has been created to automate and standardise the stakeholder identification process in the Plus Change project. The resulting list will include stakeholder specifications for all practice cases.

- 1. Please identify the stakeholder according to the listed categories.**
- 2. After submitting the form, proceed to identify the next stakeholder.**

We appreciate your cooperation!

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* Indicates required question

Email *

Your email address

Practice case *

Stakeholder name (or initials or similar) *

Your answer

Occupation / Job *

Your answer

Main stake *

- Ownership
- Decision making
- Expertise
- Use and Profit
- Interest
- Dissemination
- Other:

Stakeholder group *

(which category best describes the stakeholder)

- Major landowners (e.g. large-scale owners or land tenants)
- Minor landowners (e.g. small-scale landowners, personal use, urbanization perspective)
- Central government (e.g. ministries and other central authorities)
- Regional government (e.g. authorities, state administration and specialised agencies)
- Local government - more municipalities (e.g. municipalities, members of councils and offices)
- Local government - single municipality (e.g. municipality, members of councils and offices)
- Environmental and nature agencies (e.g. professional organisations and agencies, experts and advisors)
- Planning authorities and agencies (e.g. planning and development agencies, experts and advisors)
- Property developers and investors (e.g. investors in construction or other business)
- Natural resources managers (e.g. agricultural holdings, forest managers, farmers, operators of water sources, mining, hunting, fishing, etc.)
- Manufacturing sector (e.g. both larger or smaller companies, local business)
- NGOs and civic sector
- Active citizens
- Media
- Advocates (e.g. prominent national/regional personalities - ambassadors, champions)
- Tourism
- Other:

Position *

- Internal (stakeholder lives in the area)
- Associated (stakeholder is involved in various activities, relationships, historical ties, or cooperations in the area. This position goes beyond external stakeholders while not owning nor living in the area)
- External (stakeholder operates or has stake in the area)
- Other:

Engagement *

- Primary (directly affected by the project topic)
- Secondary (indirectly affected by the project topic)
- Other:

Influence / Power *

(according to decision making possibilities. This is meant as stakeholder relation to priority issues/challenges in a practice case.)

Choose ▼

Expertise / Knowledge *

(according to the level of knowledge)

Choose ▼

Interest / Motivation / Commitment level *

- Leader
- Supporter
- Neutral / Unbiased
- Adversarial / Resistant
- Other:

Stakeholder priority *

(the degree of stakeholder importance from a project perspective)

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